

Resource assessment for a European modelling service

Deliverable D8.2

Work package 8

Modelling infrastructure and expertise

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Executive summary

A distinguishing feature of ISBE is its ambition to provide *modelling as a service*, making it easier for biologists to integrate mathematical modelling in their scientific work. In this deliverable we review the rationale for modelling in systems biology, develop concepts to describe modelling needs and competences, cite the chief demands voiced by respondents in ISBE surveys, and propose design principles for ISBE modelling services.

The purpose of modelling is to integrate data and knowledge into a unified, predictive whole, generalizing insights from the model to a broader class of systems. However, many modelling activities require a large and highly specialized skillset that few biologists have. The main goal of ISBE modelling services is to empower the experimental research community to make modelling part of their lab routine. Thus, there is a particular focus on industry and research fields that have not traditionally identified themselves with the "systems biology" community. Model developers will benefit from easier exploration of alternative models or modelling frameworks, and in obtaining data for model building, testing and validation, all annotated for discoverability and interoperability through ISBE's data and model stewardship activities. ISBE will let biologists become modellers with less frustration, better reproducibility and higher throughput by outsourcing the technical tedium to ISBE. The aim of systems biology training and education should be to make biologists *articulated users* of modelling, not necessarily top-notch computational instrument makers.

Surveys of user needs are limited by the lack of an agreed-upon classification of modelling formalisms and activities, but the chief demands in ISBE surveys of prospective clients were access to expertise in modelling and integration (48%) and to modelling tools and resources (32%). To meet these demands, we propose the following design principles for ISBE modelling services:

- **Empowerment.** ISBE modelling services will lower the threshold for biologists to incorporate computational modelling in their scientific work.
- **A range of service levels.** ISBE should cater both to routine modelling needs and more involved model development.
- **Driven by user demands.** Focus first on modelling frameworks that have a large potential user base and can span a large space of questions with a well-defined set of query parameters. For more involved consultancy, ISBE can play a unique role in mediating contact between experimentalists and modellers.
- **Cooperation with existing communities.** Prominent members of COMBINE and of the major model repositories have been involved in discussions towards pilot "ISBE light" services.
- **Interoperability.** Common standards for the exchange and reuse of knowledge are a prerequisite for offering modelling as a service, and ISBE will be part of international initiatives for standardization.

Contents

Executive summary	3
1 Introduction and overview	5
1.1 Objectives	5
1.2 Why modelling?	5
1.3 Why modelling as a <i>service</i> ?	6
1.4 Modelling as a service: A distinguishing feature of ISBE	7
1.5 Empowering biological researchers, clinicians, and industry	8
1.6 About this document	9
2 A language to describe modelling needs and competences	10
3 Demand: Survey of modelling methodology needs	12
3.1 Surveys of potential clients and providers of modelling services	12
3.2 Education and training of potential clients	12
4 Supply: Assessment of current modelling competence and future needs	13
4.1 Education and training of service providers	13
5 Design principles of modelling services	14
5.1 Empowerment	14
5.2 A range of service levels	14
5.3 Driven by user demands	14
5.4 Cooperation with existing communities	15
5.5 FAIRDOM: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable Data, Operations and Models	15
5.6 Routing requests	16
5.7 Funding and incentives	17
6 Future development of modelling approaches	18
7 Appendices	19
7.1 Tenazinha and Vinga's classification of modelling frameworks for biological networks	19
7.2 Modeling formalisms identified in Machado et al. (2011)	19
7.3 Model categories at cellml.org	20
7.4 Gene ontology classification of models at biomodels.net	21
7.5 Mathematical Modelling Ontology (MAMO)	23
8 References	25

1 Introduction and overview

1.1 Objectives

This document assesses the outlook for ISBE to provide *modelling as a service*, making it easier for biologists to integrate mathematical modelling in their scientific work. The introduction explains why this is a good idea, while subsequent chapters explore the current and future demand and supply for modelling services, then propose design principles and strategies for putting such services into action.

1.2 Why modelling?

Biological data is now being produced in such amounts that it can only be fathomed with the help of computational modelling. For a long time, biologists could complete their careers with no mathematics and little statistical schooling, relying purely on conceptual models of how biological systems work. On the other hand, theoretical biologists have traditionally been limited by data availability, relatively safe from confrontation with empirical fact. This is changing under the omics revolution, and neither experimental nor theoretical biologists can ignore the new opportunities for large-scale linking of mental models with biological data through mathematical models.

A **model** is a *purposeful simplification* of reality, designed to imitate certain phenomena or characteristics of a system while downplaying non-essential aspects. Its value lies in the ability to generalise insights from the model to a broader class of systems. Thus, a lab mouse can be a model representing mammals in general; an *in vitro* heart cell can represent the cells in an intact heart; and a set of differential equations can approximate the dynamic behaviour of a biological system (Vik et al. 2014).

There are several benefits to building a *mathematical* model of a given class of biological systems. Mathematical analysis can reveal previously unrecognized implications of existing knowledge or assumptions, thereby deducing new insights or disproving false hypotheses. Furthermore, having a mathematical model for a class of systems makes clear both what these systems have in common (the mathematical form of the equations) and how they differ (in their respective parameter values). Therefore, *parameter estimation*, i.e. the fitting of new data to existing models, is of tremendous importance as a means to compare biological systems in a meaningful fashion. Parameters are model-based phenotypes (Gjuvsland et al. 2013) that condense vast numerical phenotypic data into fewer, more relevant measures.

However, there is usually not one single mathematical model for any given biological system, but rather a suite of models with different purposes, simplifying assumptions and data requirements. It can be argued that one does not model a *system* so much as a set of *phenomena* (Cooper et al. 2015). Instead, the word "system" in systems biology emphasizes that the phenomena of interest are explained in terms of components that mutually depend on and affect each other, to make up a functional whole.

Each of these components can be modelled in more or less detail, depending on the research question, available data and knowledge, and computational cost. Indeed, most new models arise by modification of existing ones (Smith, Crampin, et al. 2007, Waltemath et al. 2013), refining a component of interest according to some objective -- perhaps to accommodate more complex experimental data, perhaps to require *less* data that may be expensive to acquire, perhaps to be computationally cheaper while still good enough. Many such examples can be found in the history of multi-level, multi-physics modelling of the heartbeat in sickness and health, which was reviewed in Deliverable D8.1 and ISBE publication *Success Stories in Systems Biology*, 2015. It is a very powerful demonstration of how mathematical modelling serves to synthesize intellectual capital from multiple disciplines (Gjuvslund et al. 2013). ISBE will foster such synthesis of the data and knowledge generated and made available by the other European research infrastructures¹.

1.3 Why modelling as a *service*?

A main reason why biologists would want modelling services is that doing modelling properly requires a large and highly specialized skillset that few biologists have. Mathematics alone is not enough; the equations must be coded in a computer language for numerical analysis such as forward simulation and sensitivity analysis. Statistical training is required to estimate model parameters and quantify variation between specimens. Information science is essential in linking together knowledge that may have been annotated with different vocabularies or reside in different databases. Many if not most publications in computational or systems biology suffer from shortcomings in one or more of these areas.

On the positive side, many modelling concepts are straightforward in principle even though they require considerable skill and experience to reliably put into practice. For example: 1) *Integration of dynamical systems*. A heart biologist must appreciate the key notion that physiological processes *change* the physiological state, but process rates also *depend on* that state. She will also know that the voltage upstroke of a heart cell is a very fast process of sodium ions flowing into the cell, whereas the subsequent outflow is much slower. But the numerical challenges in simulating such a system with very different time-scales should be dealt with by an expert in solver software. 2) *Sensitivity analysis* requires the system

A particularly famous case of model refinement is James Clerk Maxwell's addition of a "displacement current" to Ampère's circuital law (Maxwell 1861). Albert Einstein described its impact thus:

"Imagine [Maxwell's] feelings when the differential equations he had formulated proved to him that electromagnetic fields spread in the form of polarised waves, and at the speed of light! To few men in the world has such an experience been vouchsafed... it took physicists some decades to grasp the full significance of Maxwell's discovery, so bold was the leap that his genius forced upon the conceptions of his fellow-workers." (Einstein 1940)

¹ See overview at <http://www.biomedbridges.eu/biomedical-sciences-research-infrastructures>.

biologist to decide on an informative measure of experimental outcome, and which parameter to vary and within which bounds. But parallelizing numerical experiments across a computing cluster is better left to a programmer, and a biocurator could more rapidly fetch published estimates for the focal parameters. 3) *Parameter estimation* is largely intuitive, tweaking model settings until simulation output matches observed data. But a model user needs to realize that a data set or experiment may fail to separately identify all model parameters, so that a whole subspace of parameter space matches equally well. Given this awareness, the numerical exercises of optimization can be safely left to the experts.

We envision that there will be multiple kinds of services connected with modelling, and they will span a range of service levels. Simple web pages will suffice for highly standardized analyses where users can pose a wide range of biological questions just by filling in a form and possibly uploading own data or models, similar to what is already commonplace in bioinformatics (Schattner 2008). At the other end of the spectrum, the development of novel mathematical models is as much a craft as a science, usually with multiple options every step of the way, and lots of tacit knowledge about what may work well or not. However, one rarely starts from scratch, and many biologists might appreciate support in adding or refining model components, e.g. to reflect a newly-discovered ion channel in a heart cell (Smith, Crampin, et al. 2007). Finally, data and model stewardship is a very important kind of service for modelling. Putting clients' data (Salimi & Vita 2006) or models (Li et al. 2010) into annotated, standardized form makes them interoperable with other data and model resources and ISBE services. Examples of potential ISBE modelling services are concretized in Deliverable D8.3.

In summary, by outsourcing the technical tedium to ISBE, biologists could become modellers with less frustration, better reproducibility (Peng 2011) and higher throughput. The aim of systems biology training and education (See ISBE Business plan section 3.2.6) should be to make biologists *articulated users* of modelling, not necessarily top-notch computational instrument makers.

1.4 Modelling as a service: A distinguishing feature of ISBE

It is a design goal of European research infrastructures (RIs) that they complement each other and work well together. Other RIs offer vast amounts of data, various assays and analysis methods, and aim to provide a unified interface to these pieces of knowledge. Complementary to this, ISBE modelling services will be key to refining and integrating the knowledge and data produced and made available through other RIs. For example, multilevel heart modelling can integrate knowledge on structural biology from the Instruct RI, sequence information made available via the Elixir RI, phenotypic data from mouse models via the Infrafrontier RI, and population variability from clinical research facilitated by the ECRIN RI. Very specific links from model-derived hypotheses to experimental verification can be built with EATRIS's catalogues of chemical "tool compounds" to perturb or control very specific parts of cellular biology. Likewise, many phenotypes can be defined in terms of shared and standardized experimental protocols, which can be mirrored in models; voltage-

clamping of heart cells is a prime example (Cooper et al. 2015). The interfaces between ISBE and other RIs are further reviewed in Section 7 of the ISBE Business Case.

In its data generation and stewardship activities, ISBE will work to make datasets "FAIR compliant", i.e. findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable, by annotating them with the same standardized vocabularies as used for models (see Section 3.2.2 of the ISBE Business Case). Thus, ISBE will enable faster, better research by streamlining model development and application, whether data and models are provided by clients, within ISBE, or by other research infrastructures (see Deliverable D2.2). By making it easier to link models to experiments and data, ISBE will empower experimentalists to make modelling part of their lab routine.

How to provide such services is discussed in later chapters, and is also the subject of the upcoming deliverable D8.3. For now we note that ISBE member countries are free to choose their profile along the spectrum of ISBE service levels, from web interfaces to consultancy on model development for research projects.

1.5 Empowering biological researchers, clinicians, and industry

It is a main goal of ISBE to empower the experimental research community to make modelling part of their lab routine. Thus, there is a particular focus on industry and research fields that have not traditionally identified themselves with the "systems biology" community. With ISBE services it will no longer be necessary for a research group or consortium to master all phases of the ideal modelling cycle: wet lab, omics, mathematics, high-performance computing, and so on. However, modelling will not be something that happens only inside the ISBE service apparatus -- for modelling to be useful, it must be an active part of the client's own practice. It is up to the client at which level they wish to be involved. At a minimum, the client will formulate a biological question or scenario for existing models, then make up their biological interpretation of the model output. Others may wish to extend model formulations or try out different numerical analyses. Over time, this active involvement will build experience and foster awareness of the possibilities and limitations of modelling. This ties in with training and education as discussed in Section 3.2.6 of the ISBE Business Plan.

The ISBE user base may be classified partly by scientific discipline, and partly by their methodological emphasis, e.g. on wet lab vs bioinformatics vs mathematical modelling. Furthermore, customers in academia, the health sector, and industry may demand different services of the ISBE product catalogue. Possible scenarios include:

- **“Crunch my data”**: Parameter estimation for a customer's chosen model.
- **“Model my data”**: Advise on modelling framework for customer's data.
- **“Test my model”**: Real-world lab test of a model-framed hypothesis.
- **“All inclusive”**: Test a good idea with models and data without actually owning a lab, computing cluster, or mathematical modeller.

The ISBE user base will be further described along these dimensions in the chapter "Demand: Survey of modelling methodology needs". There we also review established

solutions for data and model knowledge management, and the need for training and support of both users and providers of modelling services.

1.6 About this document

ISBE Work Package 8, *Modelling infrastructure and expertise*, aims to *provide the scientific and organisational foundation for a rapid and highly coordinated pan-European implementation of modelling as a service, for academia and industry across all major disciplinary fields of biology.*

This document, Deliverable D8.2, marks the fulfilment of Task 8.2, set out as follows: *Assess and dimension key resources for a European modelling service.* The Description of Work for this task was as follows:

- *Make a survey over major modelling methodology needs across a whole range of disciplinary categories of European biology in academia and industry.*
- *Identify existing modelling competences in Europe and assess these against the demands associated with a massive expansion of theoretical-experimental academic and industrial biological research in Europe.*
- *Identify the needs for putative new modelling approaches.*
- *Identify the data resolution needs for various modelling approaches.*
- *Identify key designs of model repositories (structure and management) that facilitate their use in education and academic and industrial research.*
- *Identify the organisational and infrastructural needs of the modelling community so that it can provide an efficient service to the European biological and biomedical research communities.*

References to sections of the Business Plan follow the headings and section numbering of version "ISBE BP 24JUN15 AP.docx".

2 A language to describe modelling needs and competences

The modelling needs of potential ISBE clients can be described along several axes:

- What biological questions they typically ask
- What kinds of data they have (biological material, experimental protocols, measurement technologies)
- What mathematical frameworks can represent the relevant biological processes and phenomena
- Need for guidance in navigating available data sets and modelling services
- Need for education and training in modelling and systems biology

This focus of this section is *modelling methodologies*, informally defined in deliverable D8.1 as the intersection of a mathematical framework, a law of nature, and a set of key assumptions; these components are what enable inference from observed data. An authoritative listing of modelling methodologies in these terms does not yet exist, and is not necessary for the pilot services to follow the ISBE pre-proposal phase (see deliverable D8.3). However, such a classification will become increasingly important as ISBE grows to offer more kinds of modelling, handle more client requests, and manage more data, models and expertise. There are many benefits to clearly identifying kinds of modelling, their required inputs and domains of application:

- It provides a quick introduction to people unfamiliar with the framework.
- It enables categorization of client needs and provider capabilities for ISBE modelling services. This is useful for structuring the ISBE service catalogue and routing client requests to available expertise.
- It clarifies what models are applicable to a given biological dataset. What features (components, variables, parameters) must a model contain to be eligible for a given experiment? What variables, collected under what circumstances, must a dataset contain to be useful in validating a given behavioural aspect of a model? For many potential ISBE clients, the easiest starting point for stating their modelling needs may be to describe what kind of data they work with.

In summary, classifying models and identifying their inputs and outputs (eventually using ontological annotation) serve to define *interfaces*, between clients and providers, and between data and models.

This is part of the greater endeavour of *interoperability* (see also Section 5.5)². The vast knowledge embodied in genomic and phenomic databases and model repositories can only be used effectively together if data and models are properly labelled, allowing data and

² The rest of this paragraph has previously been published in Omholt et al. (2013).

model resources to speak the same language. This requires formal representations of knowledge, called *ontologies*, which are lists that uniquely identify concepts and the relations between them within a specific domain (de Bono et al. 2011, Gennari et al. 2011). Thus, labels such as "abnormal enlargement of liver cells" can be given a precise technical meaning, allowing consistent exploration and querying of multiple data and model resources by bioinformatics means. Even data that is private (patient details, intellectual property, or preliminary work) can be publicly labelled, thus making potential users aware that such data exist, after which access can be negotiated. Such labelling and cross-referencing is already in place for many -omics databases, whereas for model repositories it has just started. Ontologies exist for anatomy, medical terms, gene function, protein structure, and so on. The BioPortal at bioontology.org gives a human-friendly overview (Noy et al. 2009).

Although no definite system for model classification has yet emerged, various authors and repositories have adopted a range of pragmatic approaches. Some specific examples are given in the Appendices; here is a brief overview.

- The Physiome Model Repository [groups models based on biological phenomenon](#) in an *ad hoc* manner (see Appendix 7.3), but tools now exist for ontological annotation of CellML models (Garny & Hunter 2015).
- [BioModels](#) annotates models with [gene ontology](#) terms for processes, structures and functions and lets users browse or search by GO terms (see Appendix 7.4). This permits both identification of a class of models e.g. of a given *phenomenon/process* (e.g. ion-channel transport) and of instances of that model applied to e.g. specific *organelles*. (Higher levels of biological organization, e.g. *cell types*, are outside the domain of GO but can be annotated with other ontologies (Smith, Ashburner, et al. 2007).) In addition, BioModels extensively annotate taxonomic species for which the model is relevant, diseases associated (increasingly using [Experimental Factor Ontology](#)) as well as additional information on the nature and roles of model components (using [Systems Biology Ontology](#)). Much of this additional information can be accessed through the search facility on the website.
- The [Mathematical Modelling Ontology](#) (MAMO) was initiated by members of the ISBE pre-proposal. MAMO describes each model class in words, with citation of key articles (or Wikipedia entries). This enables clear identification of the kinds of models included. The MAMO ontology itself is *unpopulated*, that is, it contains classes (kinds of models) but no instances (specific models of the same type). However, models at biomodels.net are increasingly being annotated with MAMO terms. Appendix 7.5 lists the identifiers defined at the time of writing.
- For constraint-based models, Lewis et al. have constructed a "phylogeny" of subdisciplines and kinds of analysis (Lewis et al. 2012).
- Tenazinha and Vinga have classified modelling frameworks for biological networks (Tenazinha & Vinga 2011), summarized in Appendix 7.1.
- Machado et al. offer a classification of modelling formalisms for systems biology (Machado et al. 2011), summarized in Appendix 7.2.

- Groen and coauthors have developed a taxonomy of multiscale and multiphysics applications (Groen et al. 2011, 2014).
- Sloot and Hoekstra have developed a framework for describing how different-scale components interface in multiscale models (Sloot & Hoekstra 2010).
- Categorizations in encyclopedias and scientific journals are generally poorly structured with respect to the relationships between entities, showing inconsistency in the granularity of terms at different levels. They therefore are of limited help in structuring information so as to navigate or analyze it.

3 Demand: Survey of modelling methodology needs

3.1 Surveys of potential clients and providers of modelling services

ISBE has conducted surveys of potential clients of systems biology services in academia, industries and the health sector (see ISBE Deliverable D15.1). While many potential user groups see a use for modelling in their interpretation and analysis of data, few can be very specific about the modelling methodology they need. More often it is clearer what kind of *data* they have, and so it would be very helpful to identify what kinds of data are amenable to what kinds of analysis (see also Section 5.6). Industry has the potential to act as both a provider and user of ISBE modelling services. An ISBE survey of companies active in systems biology (D15.1) has understandably identified modelling as a major area of interest for these. 96% of those surveyed use modelling tools in their operations and of those 48% suggested that access to modelling and integration expertise was a major challenge they face, while 32% cited an improvement in accessibility of modelling tools and resources as potentially beneficial. A significant benefit of ISBE could be to act as a marketplace for both academic and industrial users and providers of modelling services. As for providers, WP3's interviews will shed light on the heterogeneous distribution of modelling potential and expertise across European countries.

3.2 Education and training of potential clients

Education and training are important parts of empowering biologists to become articulated users of modelling. Here, "education" refers to teaching at universities, while "training" refers to post-graduate and life-long competence and skill acquisition, including for non-"systems biologists". Training options for different user groups (academic, clinical, industrial) are outlined in section 3.2.6 of the ISBE Business Plan. ISBE's survey of representatives of the industrial community, including a range of sectors and sizes of operation from SMEs to large multinationals suggests that training is a primary concern, with half of those surveyed suggesting that access to suitable systems biology training was a significant challenge for their industry. Of those, 77% would favour an improvement in the provision of training in predictive modelling. ISBE will inform about available training through the ISBE community website, and train clients in the use of ISBE tools and services. End-user training will be developed in collaboration with other research infrastructures such as Elixir, because systems biology ties together multiple disciplines and data sources.

4 Supply: Assessment of current modelling competence and future needs

A vast competence in modelling is potentially reachable through academic associations (e.g. the International Union of the Physiological Sciences) and umbrella projects (e.g. the Virtual Physiological Human, and ISBE itself) related to systems biology. In addition, many kinds of nonbiological expertise are essential to systems biology, for instance in parameter estimation, mathematical analysis, experimental design, measurement technologies, information management, etc.

Charting this competence faces the same challenge as for modelling needs: There is no agreed-upon classification of kinds of modelling. As a consequence, the routing of clients to providers must initially rely on the overview and tacit knowledge of individual staff in ISBE centres (national or central). Such an arrangement should be workable for a limited assortment of services, and as ISBE staff gain familiarity with user needs, the links from user needs to provider capabilities may emerge organically, growing like synapses in a nerve network, strengthened by repeated interaction. This ensures a user-driven focus and development of modelling services, including a vocabulary and ontology for modelling frameworks.

The best-charted competences are perhaps those reflected in existing model repositories (BioModels, the Physiome Model Repository, and JWS online). These all have some level of model characterization (whether ad-hoc subject headings or GO terms), the community of model authors or curators are familiar with entire families of models, and many in their associated research communities are familiar with the concepts of standardization, annotation and interoperability. Section 5.7 on funding and incentives addresses the crucial question of why experts should wish to provide services within an ISBE setting. And in Deliverable D8.3, we outline how these repositories and communities can form the basis for ISBE light services.

4.1 Education and training of service providers

The education of future systems biologists to provide modelling services is a key task for ISBE, as discussed in section 3.2.6 in the Business Plan. The current assortment of university programmes for systems biology was surveyed in ISBE deliverable D10.1. A major finding was that programmes explicitly labelled "systems biology" were largely limited to countries with past strategic investment in systems biology. A core curriculum for the education of future systems biologists was developed in two workshops held jointly by ISBE and ERASysAPP (see D10.2 and D13.2), and will be disseminated through journal publication and implemented through Erasmus+ ³ and national systems biology centres (nSBCs) in due course.

³ <http://ec.europa.eu/programmes/erasmus-plus>

5 Design principles of modelling services

Based on the abovementioned surveys and interviews, discussions within ISBE, and dialogue with standards and repository communities, we suggest the following principles for the design of ISBE modelling services.

5.1 Empowerment

ISBE modelling services aim to lower the threshold for biologists to incorporate computational modelling in their scientific work. Clients should be active participants in the interaction with ISBE tools and expertise; this will build competence and expand the range of activities that clients can do on their own.

Target communities for these services include academia and industry, wet-lab and dry-lab and computational biologists, with varying levels of training in mathematics, statistics, computer and information science.

5.2 A range of service levels

ISBE should cater both to routine modelling needs and more involved model development. Thus, there will be multiple kinds of services connected with modelling, ranging from easy-to-use interactive web tools, to scriptable web services, to guidance in available online and offline tools, to more involved consultancy in model development.

5.3 Driven by user demands

To ensure that ISBE services grow in a direction that is relevant to many biologists, we suggest that expansion of ISBE services focus on actual demands by users. For the initial selection of ISBE light services, we propose to focus first on modelling frameworks that have:

- A large potential user base
- Fairly standardized ways of asking research questions, so that one can span a large space of questions with a well-defined set of query parameters⁴.

Then users can pose a wide range of biological questions just by filling in a form and possibly uploading own data or models, similar to what is already commonplace in bioinformatics (Schattner 2008). Specific suggestions are given in the "first modelling services" section below.

⁴ One example is sensitivity analysis (regional or local), where results will vary depending on your chosen region or point in (biological or experimental) parameter space. Another example is voltage clamping of excitable nerve or heart cells. There is a large range of ion channels and cells subtypes that can be investigated within a family of experimental protocols specified through the choice of ion channel and a time-series of voltage clamps designed to interrogate the particular system in question.

For more involved consultancy, ISBE can play a unique role in mediating contact between experimentalists and modellers. Whether and how this is done will depend on funders and national systems biology centres.

5.4 Cooperation with existing communities

It is crucial to ISBE's credibility in unifying systems biology services in Europe that it gain active involvement from all the communities with vested interests in modelling tools and services, such as the Virtual Physiological Human, the International Society for Systems Biology, the Physiome Model Repository, the BioModels repository, and the JWS Online repository and modelling tools. A key initiative for standardization and interoperability is the COMBINE (computational modeling in biology network, co.mbine.org) network, covering the data formats BioPAX, SBGN, SBML, SED-ML and CellML, and associated with the standardization efforts MIRIAM, SBO, KiSAO and BioModels⁵. Prominent members of COMBINE and of the major model repositories have been involved in discussions towards pilot "ISBE light" services.

5.5 FAIRDOM: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable Data, Operations and Models

Systems biology relies on the joining of data and model resources, and so interoperability is a key feature of ISBE activities. Indeed, the strongest demand from participants in the ISBE telephone survey⁶ was for the generation of standardized data that can be integrated in computer models. Careful annotation and FAIRDOM (see Deliverable D2.2 and ISBE Business plan Appendix 7) will make it as easy as possible to join together data, models and experimental setups in new ways, provided they deal with the same quantities.

Interoperability is also a goal for user interfaces. ISBE aims to harmonize the interfaces to systems biology services both within ISBE and those run by partners, so that users of one service will quickly find their way around another. By mastering a fairly small set of basic skills in annotation and querying, ISBE clients should have access to a vast repository of knowledge to interface with their own.

Many of the requisite markup languages, ontologies, annotation practices and knowledge management systems have already been developed, as reviewed in Deliverable D2.2 (see also FORCE 11 2014). ISBE will have several activities linked to common standards:

- Adapting existing tools and standards to play together within an overarching ISBE interface.
- Improving and standardizing the annotation of existing data and models.
- Fostering the further development of tools and standards.

⁵ en.wikipedia.org/wiki/COMBINE

⁶ Telephone survey of senior level academic scientists and medical researchers, conducted by Instinctif partners

Much of this work can be prioritized and driven by client requests. New clients will receive ISBE assistance in bringing relevant data and/or models into standard form. ISBE will ensure that model output and published results are well annotated. This ensures reusability, reproducibility, quality assurance, and integrative accumulation of knowledge, all of which are key concerns for funders and society.

We also expect that ISBE modelling consultancy will often yield reusable workflows that can be turned into web services for application by wider user groups.

5.6 Routing requests

As discussed in the introduction, the routing of clients to providers can initially rely on the overview of individual ISBE staff for a limited assortment of services. Eventually, ISBE will need to develop some kind of browsable product catalogue and directory of ISBE expertises, data and model resources. Basing this development on client demand ensures a user-driven focus and development of modelling services. This extends to developing a vocabulary and ontology for modelling frameworks, including a systematic overview of the problem domains and data requirements of given models. For many clients, their existing or upcoming data is the natural starting point, and relevant modelling approaches can be identified with the help of a decision tree as in Figure 1.

Figure 1. "Decision tree" showing the data requirements for different kinds of metabolic and biochemical signalling models. This is also helpful for ISBE clients who "have data, want model" in identifying applicable modelling approaches, and points out what additional data would be required to include additional aspects of the system. (From Kahlem et al. 2011, Open Access.)

5.7 Funding and incentives

The benefits to *clients* of modelling services were laid out in the introduction. To encourage new clients to try out ISBE services, the first hours of service could be free for the client. For example, the first week of support in an initial marketing period, and perhaps the first day for routine operation. Once ISBE services have established a strong reputation, ISBE might establish a pricing model where end users pay for services and budget for these in grant proposals. This question is similar to that faced by other research infrastructures such as Elixir.

But what can motivate highly qualified modellers to *provide* such services instead of pursuing more traditional careers? This is a difficult question that must be tackled jointly by ISBE and national funding agencies.

With adequate funding, modelling could become a new career path similar to biocuration, with schooling in a standard curriculum of methods and no expectation of coauthorship.

While this will cover many common demands, many if not most applications of modelling in biology require substantial intellectual input, as seen in the "modelling success stories" reviewed in Deliverable D8.1.

Another option is for modellers to provide service while also building their own competence and scientific track record, implemented as follows. National centres award ISBE postdoc fellowships (competitively) to people who receive "ISBE-certified" training and then work in various experimental labs in academia or industry. This ensures that the national centres support end-users in their country, while adhering to common standards and remaining interoperable with international data and model resources, and keeps the modellers close to the wet-lab experts.

Thus, ISBE modelling services might involve three categories of people, each funded in different ways: Curators and developers that belong to the hub; full-time ISBE modellers that train others and can also be assigned to projects; and the ISBE-approved postdocs outlined above.

6 Future development of modelling approaches

The systems biology community and funders need to ensure the development of new modelling approaches to meet the evolving needs of systems biology. This needs to be driven by need and not imposed by ISBE. However, ISBE will be well suited to coordinate discussions to identify areas in need of further development, for instance virtual experiments (Cooper et al. 2015) for the rigorous, streamlined confrontation between experimental datasets and candidate models, and multiscale and multiphysics modelling of processes that occur on very different scales of time or space (see showcase on multiscale heart modelling in Deliverable D8.1).

A roadmap for initial ISBE modelling services and strategies for growth is presented in Deliverable D8.3, Section 6.

7 Appendices

7.1 Tenazinha and Vinga's classification of modelling frameworks for biological networks

These are numbered section headings from Tenazinha and Vinga (2011), see also their Table 1.

2. Structural and stoichiometric modeling
 - 2.1 Network-based analysis
 - 2.1.1 (Hyper)graph-based analysis
 - 2.1.2 Elementary flux modes/extreme pathway analysis
 - 2.2 Constraints-based modeling
 - 2.2.1 Regulated flux balance analysis
 - 2.2.2 Steady-state regulated flux balance analysis
 - 2.2.3 Integrated flux balance analysis
 - 2.2.4 Integrated dynamic flux balance analysis
 - 2.3 Chemical organization theory
- 3 Kinetic modeling
 - 3.1 Discrete models
 - 3.1.1 Logical-based models
 - 3.1.2 Petri net modeling
 - 3.2 Continuous models
 - 3.3 Hybrid modeling
 - 3.4 Stochastic modeling

7.2 Modeling formalisms identified in Machado et al. (2011)

- Boolean networks
- Bayesian networks
- Petri nets
- Process algebras
- Constraint-based models
- Differential equations
- Rule-based models
- Interacting state machines
- Cellular automata
- Agent-based models

7.3 Model categories at cellml.org

CellML is mostly used to represent sets of ordinary differential equations⁷. Electrophysiological models often contain Markov submodels⁸ for state transitions in ion channels. If the rate equations involve rootfinding, that turns the models into differential algebraic equations⁹. (Footnotes refer to MAMO identifiers, see Appendix 7.5.)

The following categories were used at <https://models.physiomeproject.org/cellml> as of 2014-09-25:

- [Calcium Dynamics](#)
- [Cardiovascular Circulation](#)
- [Cell Cycle](#)
- [Cell Migration](#)
- [Circadian Rhythms](#)
- [Electrophysiology](#)
- [Endocrine](#)
- [Excitation-Contraction Coupling](#)
- [Gene Regulation](#)
- [Hepatology](#)
- [Immunology](#)
- [Ion Transport](#)
- [Mechanical Constitutive Laws](#)
- [Metabolism](#)
- [Myofilament Mechanics](#)
- [Neurobiology](#)
- [pH Regulation](#)
- [PKPD](#)
- [Signal Transduction](#)
- [Synthetic Biology](#)

⁷ Ordinary differential equation model: http://identifiers.org/mamo/MAMO_0000046

⁸ Markov model: http://identifiers.org/mamo/MAMO_00001937

⁹ Differential algebraic model: http://identifiers.org/mamo/MAMO_0000090

7.4 Gene ontology classification of models at biomodels.net

Biomodels annotates models with gene ontology terms for cellular processes, structures and functions. These assignments can be browsed graphically through a chart, or through a tree-based view.

Figure 2. Interactive browsing of BioModels by gene ontology (GO) process terms. The top-level view shows the number of models annotated with each term. Clicking on a term lists the particular models and offers narrower terms for further specification of the search.

The following list shows the number of models annotated with each Gene Ontology term from the first two levels of classification. (Copied from <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/biomodels-main/gotree> on 2014-09-25.)

- »GO:0008150 - biological_process (546)
 - »GO:0022610 - biological adhesion (1)
 - »GO:0044848 - biological phase (17)
 - »GO:0065007 - biological regulation (384)
 - »GO:0008283 - cell proliferation (11)
 - »GO:0071840 - cellular component organization or biogenesis (119)
 - »GO:0009987 - cellular process (454)
 - »GO:0016265 - death (19)

- »GO:0032502 - developmental process (31)
- »GO:0051234 - establishment of localization (177)
- »GO:0040007 - growth (11)
- »GO:0046879 - hormone secretion (14)
- »GO:0002376 - immune system process (26)
- »GO:0051179 - localization (183)
- »GO:0040011 - locomotion (6)
- »GO:0008152 - metabolic process (388)
- »GO:0051704 - multi-organism process (132)
- »GO:0032501 - multicellular organismal process (101)
- »GO:0048519 - negative regulation of biological process (77)
- »GO:0043473 - pigmentation (1)
- »GO:0048518 - positive regulation of biological process (91)
- »GO:0050789 - regulation of biological process (327)
- »GO:0000003 - reproduction (6)
- »GO:0022414 - reproductive process (5)
- »GO:0050896 - response to stimulus (279)
- »GO:0048511 - rhythmic process (42)
- »GO:0023052 - signaling (214)
- »GO:0044699 - single-organism process (521)
- »GO:0005575 - cellular_component (419)
 - »GO:0005623 - cell (409)
 - »GO:0030054 - cell junction (1)
 - »GO:0044464 - cell part (295)
 - »GO:0031012 - extracellular matrix (1)
 - »GO:0044420 - extracellular matrix part (1)
 - »GO:0005576 - extracellular region (76)
 - »GO:0044421 - extracellular region part (26)
 - »GO:0032991 - macromolecular complex (94)
 - »GO:0016020 - membrane (47)
 - »GO:0044425 - membrane part (32)
 - »GO:0031974 - membrane-enclosed lumen (19)
 - »GO:0043226 - organelle (135)
 - »GO:0044422 - organelle part (43)
 - »GO:0045202 - synapse (2)
 - »GO:0019012 - virion (1)
 - »GO:0044423 - virion part (1)
- »GO:0003674 - molecular_function (261)
 - »GO:0016209 - antioxidant activity (6)
 - »GO:0005488 - binding (121)
 - »GO:0003824 - catalytic activity (174)
 - »GO:0016247 - channel regulator activity (6)
 - »GO:0009055 - electron carrier activity (1)

- »GO:0030234 - enzyme regulator activity (38)
- »GO:0005085 - guanyl-nucleotide exchange factor activity (7)
- »GO:0060089 - molecular transducer activity (80)
- »GO:0044092 - negative regulation of molecular function (60)
- »GO:0001071 - nucleic acid binding transcription factor activity (18)
- »GO:0044093 - positive regulation of molecular function (75)
- »GO:0004872 - receptor activity (65)
- »GO:0030545 - receptor regulator activity (1)
- »GO:0065009 - regulation of molecular function (111)
- »GO:0005198 - structural molecule activity (5)
- »GO:0005215 - transporter activity (53)

7.5 Mathematical Modelling Ontology (MAMO)

The MAMO ontology can be browsed at <http://purl.bioontology.org/ontology/MAMO>. Below is a snapshot of the tree structure of MAMO as of SVN revision 40, 2014-06-27. Each model class has encoded attributes that describe its scope (e.g. the "isUsedToModel" attribute).

Thing

model

mathematical model

population model

matrix population model

differential equation model

stochastic differential equations model

ordinary differential equations model

partial differential equations model

delayed differential equation model

differential algebraic equation model

process algebra

Petri net

stochastic Petri net

hybrid Petri net

hybrid functional Petri net

continuous Petri net

functional Petri net

hybrid functional Petri net

coloured Petri net

computational model

agent-based model

cellular automaton

dynamic cellular automaton

stochastic cellular automaton

interacting state machine

rule-based model

- network model
- steady-state model
 - constraint-based model
- logical model
 - multi-value discrete model
 - boolean model
- statistical model
 - mixed model
 - logistic regression
 - multinomial logistic regression
 - Poisson regression
- Bayesian model
 - dynamic Bayesian model
- domain model
 - computational Neuroscience model
 - chemical reaction diffusion model
 - finite element spatial model
 - biochemical network
 - signalling network
 - gene regulatory network
 - metabolic network
 - multiphysics model
 - single particle spatial model
 - pharmacometrics model
 - pharmacokinetics model
 - population pharmacokinetics model
 - pharmacodynamics model
- readout
 - steady state value
 - phase portrait
 - timecourse
- variable
 - statistical data
 - longitudinal data
 - count data
 - categorical data
 - binary data
 - independent variable
 - dependent variable
- modelling entity feature
 - temporal quality
 - dynamical characteristic
 - static characteristic

quantitative characteristic
 discrete characteristic
 continuous characteristic
uncertainty level
 probabilistic nature
 deterministic nature
linear quality
spatial characteristic

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